

TRANSIENT ISCHEMIC ATTACK AS A PRECURSOR TO STROKE

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Abstract. *Transient ischemic attack, being a precursor of stroke, increases the risk of its development up to 30%. Low awareness of the population about the symptoms of TIA may be the reason of late hospitalization of patients with its development and thereby promote the occurrence of stroke and reduces the efficiency of treatment. The use of an easy-to-use ABCD2 scale (age, arterial hypertension, presence of paresis and aphasia, duration of symptoms more than 60 minutes, diabetes mellitus) may have prognostic value in the hospitalization of this type of patients. It is necessary to start secondary prevention of stroke as early as possible. The question of choosing modern methods of prevention and treatment of patients with TIA, the choice of the optimal method for the surgical treatment of patients with carotid artery stenosis has not been finally resolved. The study of this problem can provide more accurate criteria for the optimal choice of modern diagnostic methods, prevention and treatment of patients with transient ischemic attacks.*

Keywords: *transient ischemic attack, stroke, prognosis, pathogenesis, atherosclerosis, diagnosis, prevention, treatment.*

The problem of cerebral stroke remains of extreme social and medical importance throughout the world [1]. According to WHO, stroke is the leading cause of disability in the adult population. Violation of cerebral circulation is a concept that includes not only stroke, but also transitory cerebral circulation disturbances or transient ischemic attacks (TIA). Based on MRI data, it was found that at a TIA duration of more than 1 hour, persistent foci of ischemia appear in the brain. Therefore, at the suggestion of the World Stroke Organization, the diagnosis of TIA can be made only if the duration of symptoms does not exceed 60 minutes and is completely resolved. Otherwise, a diagnosis of stroke is made [2]. TIA, being a precursor to stroke, increases the risk of its development by up to 30%, which is 9 times higher than that in the general population [3]. To assess the risk of stroke, a special ABCD2 scale was proposed, which is used to evaluate the risk of developing an early stroke after a TIA and identify patients who should be hospitalized. This scale takes into account age over 60 years, blood pressure above 140/90 mm Hg, presence of clinical symptoms, duration of symptoms over 60 minutes, diabetes mellitus. Patients with a TIA score of 2 or more should be hospitalized for further evaluation and treatment [2]. The causes of TIA are varied. They are as follows: arterial hypertension of any origin, heart disease, atrial fibrillation, a history of myocardial infarction, dyslipoproteinemia, diabetes mellitus, asymptomatic carotid artery disease, pathology of small vessels of the brain, cervical osteochondrosis, left ventricular aneurysm, artificial heart valve, rheumatic heart valve damage, bacterial endocarditis and others. Lifestyle-related risk factors also play an important role in the development of TIA: smoking, alcohol abuse, overweight, the use of contraceptives, poor nutrition, psychoemotional stress, migraine [3,4,2,5].

The pathophysiological basis of TIA clinical manifestations is the presence of ischemic penumbra zones in the brain, which has a complex molecular-genetic, biochemical, cellular and

spatial structure, which is characterized by multifactorial dynamic transformation [1,5]. The clinical picture at the onset of TIA corresponds to an ischemic stroke and is often manifested by mild neurological disorders (numbness of the face and arm, mild hemiparesis or monoparesis, speech disorders, decreased vision in one eye are possible). TIAs can be repeated several times a day for a long time. A significant proportion of patients with ischemic stroke (20-30%) have previously experienced TIAs, which indicates their important prognostic value [1,3,7]. Atherothrombotic, embolic, hemodynamic and lacunar strokes are distinguished among ischemic strokes [7,8].

Transient ischemic attacks usually occur suddenly. Many patients often do not attach significant importance to transient short-term disorders and do not seek medical advice, so it is difficult to estimate the prevalence of TIA.

One of the main causes of extracranial artery lesions leading to cerebral ischemia is atherosclerosis. Atherosclerotic lesions of the cerebral arteries are the cause for 40-45% of all cases of ischemic disorders of cerebral circulation [6]. Currently, there is no doubt about the concept of pathogenetic heterogeneity of ischemic stroke, and the most frequent (more than a third of cases) is the atherothrombotic type associated with lesion of the extracranial arteries, primarily the carotid arteries. The hemodynamic mechanism of stroke development plays an important role at severe stenoses and occlusions of the internal carotid artery [6].

The increasing frequency of ischemic strokes (four times higher than hemorrhagic ones), the high frequency of transient ischemic attacks, lacunar cerebral infarctions, an increase in the prevalence of recurrent ischemic cerebral circulation disorders, as well as chronic progressive cerebrovascular pathology, including vascular dementia, cause intensive study of the pathogenesis, diagnostics, treatment and prevention of atherosclerotic lesions [6].

Currently existing methods of both primary and secondary prevention of cerebral circulation disorders can be divided into conservative and surgical ones. In numerous multicenter randomized trials, the efficiency of carotid artery stenosis surgical correction for the secondary prevention of cerebral circulation disorders in patients with severe (more than 60-70%) carotid stenosis who have suffered transient ischemic attacks and minor stroke has been convincingly proven [7,6]. This is especially relevant, since the risk of recurrent ischemic stroke is 10-15% during the first year, then the frequency of recurrent strokes is 5% annually, exceeding 15 times the frequency of stroke in the general population.

To date, few studies have been conducted in which a comprehensive clinical, neurological, neuropsychological examination of patients with various pathogenetic variants of TIA, namely with occlusive lesions of the brachiocephalic arteries, taking into account the localization, degree of prevalence and structural features of atherosclerotic lesions, as well as other risk factors for the development of ischemic brain disease, have been performed. The data on the effect of surgical correction of atherosclerotic carotid stenosis on clinical, neurological and neuropsychological functions are contradictory. Many authors in their research have noted the positive effect of atherosclerotic carotid stenosis surgical correction on clinical, neurological and neuropsychological functions [7,6].

All patients need to perform ultrasound examination of the carotid arteries before surgery, then the issue of choosing a surgical treatment method is solved. When solving the issue of surgical treatment, the degree of cerebral artery stenosis, the prevalence of atherosclerotic lesions, the age

of the patient, as well as the presence of concomitant somatic diseases are always taken into account (8).

All surgeries are aimed on the elimination of cerebral artery stenosis and are divided into 2 types: carotid endarterectomy (CE) and an alternative to CE is a minimally invasive endovascular intervention with the installation of a stent (Smout J., 2010).

Carotid angioplasty and stenting (CAS) for the prevention of ischemic stroke has been used since the mid-80s. CAS reduces the painfulness of manipulations and the hospital-stay and also does not leave postoperative scars, compared with CE. The absence of the need for general anesthesia is another great advantage of the endovascular technique. Modern X-ray endovascular approaches during stenting of cerebral arteries allow to perform surgeries as early as possible from the moment of the disease. This method is also highly effective with careful selection for elderly patients [8,7,6].

Conclusions. Thus, low awareness of the population about the symptoms of TIA may be the reason for late hospitalization of patients with its development and thereby promotes the occurrence of stroke and a decrease in the effectiveness of treatment.

It is necessary to start secondary prevention of stroke as early as possible, because most ischemic strokes in patients who have undergone TIA occur in the first days after the disease.

Further study of risk factors for each of the methods is relevant. Considering that such measures are an effective alternative to drug therapy, a comparative dynamic study of the condition of patients undergoing stenting of the internal carotid artery, CE and patients receiving drug therapy is of undoubted interest. It is necessary to study short-term and long-term effects.

The aim of treating patients with TIA is to prevent subsequent TIA and the development of stroke.

The study of this problem can provide more accurate criteria for the optimal choice of modern methods for diagnostics, prevention and treatment of patients with transient ischemic attacks.

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